

Figure S1: A_2 vibrational normal mode at 334 cm^{-1} computed at the 1^1A_2 state in its equilibrium geometry.

Figure S2: SA-CASSCF natural orbitals defining the (10,10) active space of the $\text{NH}_2\text{-2CN}$ aryl nitrene derivative.

Spin polarized intersystem crossing analysis

Following the reference cartesian system adopted in Figure 2 of the main text, within the C_{2v} point group, the spatial symmetry of the spin-orbit coupling (SOC) operator is totally symmetric (A_1). The spin functions of the three triplet sublevels are associated with the irreducible representations (IRs) A_2 , B_1 and B_2 . The SOC integrals assisting the (reverse) intersystem crossing channels, (R)ISC, satisfy the following symmetry criteria:

Table S1: symmetry analysis of the SOC integrals assisting the (R)ISC pathways; the “active IR” is the irreducible representation for which the direct product of the IRs is equal to the totally symmetric IR.

Integral	Symmetry criteria	Active IR
Triplet to singlet ISC		
$\langle 1^3B_1 \hat{H}_{SOC} 1/2^1A_1 \rangle$	$B_1 \otimes (A_2, \mathbf{B}_1, B_2) \otimes A_1 \otimes A_1$	$B_1 \equiv \Gamma(R_x)$
$\langle 1^3B_1 \hat{H}_{SOC} 1^1A_2 \rangle$	$B_1 \otimes (A_2, B_1, \mathbf{B}_2) \otimes A_1 \otimes A_2$	$B_2 \equiv \Gamma(R_y)$
Singlet to triplet RISC		
$\langle 1/2^1A_1 \hat{H}_{SOC} X^3A_2 \rangle$	$A_1 \otimes A_1 \otimes A_2 \otimes (A_2, B_1, B_2)$	$A_2 \equiv \Gamma(R_z)$
$\langle 1^1A_2 \hat{H}_{SOC} X^3A_2 \rangle$	$A_2 \otimes A_1 \otimes A_2 \otimes (A_2, B_1, B_2)$	None

As shown in Table S1, the triplet sublevels involved in the ISC processes transform as the B_1 and B_2 IRs, while the one involved in the RISC processes only transforms as the A_2 IRs. These criteria enable the spin polarized (R)ISC and the following overpopulation of the A_2 triplet sublevels in the ground state (X^3A_2).